

PEREYONIMLAR – ONOMASTIK BIRLIKLARNING BIR TURI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada onomastik birliklarning bir turi bo‘lgan pereyonimlarning til va nutqdagi o‘rni, ayrim leksik-semantik xususiyatlari, tasnifi masalasiga e‘tibor qaratilgan.

Tayanch so‘zlar: onomastika, onomastik birlik, pereyonim, transport, transport nomlari, tasnif.

PEREYONYM - A TYPE OF ONOMASTIC UNITS

Abstract. This article focuses on the role of pereonyms, which are a type of onomastic units, in language and speech, some lexical-semantic features, and classification.

Key words: onomastics, onomastic unit, pereonym, transport, transport names, classification.

ПЕРЕЁНИМ - РАЗНООБРАЗИЕ ОНОМАСТИЧЕСКИХ ЕДИНИЦ

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается роль переонимов, являющихся разновидностью ономастических единиц, в языке и речи, некоторые лексико-семантические особенности, их классификация.

Ключевые слова: ономастика, ономастическая единица, переоним, транспорт, транспортные названия, классификация.

Pereyonimlar – onomastik birliklar qatorida turuvchi leksik birliklardan. Ular o‘ziga xos lisoniy-semantik, milliy-madaniy, stilistik xususiyatlarda namoyon bo‘ladi. Badiiy matnlarda poetonim sifatida ham qo‘llanib keladi.

Dunyodagi barcha tillar tizimida pereyonimlarning o‘z o‘rni bor. Ular ko‘pincha qisqartma so‘zlar ko‘rinishida uchraydi. Bir tildan ikkinchi bir tilga o‘zlashma (olinma) so‘z sifatida kirib borib, uning lug‘at tarkibini boyitishga xizmat qiladi. Bunda ular bir tildan boshqa bir tizimdagi tilga kirib borar ekan, tarjima qilinmaydi va o‘z asliyatini saqlab qolishi kuzatiladi.

Pereyonim deganda, transport vositalarining atoqli nomlari tushuniladi. Pereyonim yunoncha – “periov” so‘zidan olingan bo‘lib, “harakatlanish vositasi” degan ma‘noni anglatadi.

Ular tilda alohida leksik tizimni hosil qiladi. Ya.I.Avlakulov pereyonimlarning turlarini o‘z izlanishlarida ko‘rsatib o‘tgan.[1,98-99]

Pereyonimlarni, avvalo, qayerda qo‘llanishiga qarab to‘rtga bo‘lib o‘rganish mumkin:

1. Quruqlikda yurishga mo‘ljallangan transport vositalarining nomlari: “Ikarus” avtobusi, “Kaptiva” mashinasi, “Vosxod” mototsikli, “Tigr” tanki.

2. Suvda suzishga mo‘ljallangan transport vositalarining nomlari: “Titanik” kemasi, “Aврora” kreyseri. Bu turdagi atoqli otlarga nisbatan yunoncha “nautuxos” – flot, “onoma” – nom so‘zlaridan olingan “nautonim” atamasi ham qo‘llanadi. “Brig”, “Karavella”, “Shlyupka”, “Frechat” kabi transport kemalari, harbiy kemalar nomi bunga misol bo‘la oladi.

3. Havoda uchishga moslangan transport vositalarining nomlari: “Kukuruznik” samolyoti, “TU-24” samolyoti.

4. Rels (temir izlar) ustida yuruvchi transport vositalari: “Afrosiyob” tezyurari, “Sharq” poyezdi.

Pereyonim onomastik birlik sifatida bu kabi transport vositalarining alohida bir tipiga nisbatan qo‘llanadi. Ko‘rinadiki, ular atoqli otlar turkumiga kiradi.

O‘zbek tilida pereyonimlarning o‘zlashtirilishi o‘tgan asrning ikkinchi yarmidan kuchaygan. To mustaqillik yillarigacha tilimizga “Pobeda”, “Moskvich”, “Zaporojets”, “Zil”, “Kamaz”, “Jiguli”, “Volga” (va hokazo) kabi pereyonimlar o‘zlashtirilgan bo‘lsa, istiqlol yillarida “Mercedes-Bens”, “Damas”, “Tiko”, “Nexia”, “Matiz”, “Lacetti”, “Spark”, “Gentra” “Maserati”, “Toyota-Prado”, “Maybach”, “Ferrari”, “Ford”, “Chevrolet Captiva” kabi yengil avtomobillarning nomlari kirib keldi.

Shuni ham aytish kerakki, ushbu avtomobillarning aksariyati yurtimizda ishlab chiqarildi.

Ularning til va nutqda qo‘llanilishiga davr ham ta’sir ko‘rsatadi. Xususan, o‘tgan asrning 80-yillarida Vengriyada ishlab chiqarilgan “Ikarus” avtobuslari juda ommabop bo‘lgan. O‘sha paytlarda Yevropada ishlab chiqarilgan avtobuslarning yarmidan ko‘prog‘ini “Ikarus”lar tashkil etgan. Har yili o‘rtacha o‘n ikki ming dona avtobus ishlab chiqarilar va uning asosiy qismi SSSRga eksport qilinardi. Shu sababli sobiq ittifoqda, jumladan, O‘zbekistonda shahar va shaharlararo yo‘nalishlarda, asosan, “Ikarus” avtobuslari xizmat qilardi.[6] Shunday ekan, bu pereyonimning o‘tgan asrning oxirida o‘ta faol, hozirgi kunda nutq faoliyatida kam qo‘llanishi davr bilan bog‘liqligini dalillaydi.

Hozirgi paytda “Tiko” rusumli avtomobillar ishlab chiqarilmayapti. Ulardan aholi kam foydalanyapti, shuning uchun bu pereyonim nafaol so‘zga aylanib bormoqda. “Tracker”, “Epica” kabi avtoulavlar esa ayni kunlarda xaridorgir bo‘lganligi sababli ularning nomi ham tilda faol qo‘llanishda. Bu esa pereyonimlarning tarixiy (diaxron) va zamonaviy (sinxron) qatlamga egaligidan dalolat beradi.

Pereyonimlarni shakllantirishda uni kashf qilgan olimlar, konstruktorlar nomi yoki o‘sha transport vositasi ishlab chiqilgan zavod, shahar nomi asos qilib olingani ko‘p kuzatiladi.

Jumladan, “AN-24”, “An-124” passajir samolyotlari [7], “Il-76” harbiy-transport samolyoti [8], “Il-86” “Il-96” transport samolyotlari [9], “TU-104”, “TU-154” avialaynerlari, “Moskvich”, “Volga-24” avtomobillari, “Belarus”, “Altay” traktorlari, “Kamaz” yuk mashinasi kabilar buning yorqin misollaridir.

“Nexia” so‘zining ma‘nosi “Qaldirg‘och” degani. Hozirda uning Ravon Nexia, Chevrolet Nexia kabi turlari mavjud.

“Chevrolet Malibu” pereyonimi tarkibidagi “Malibu” so‘zi inglizcha bo‘lib, AQSh shaharlaridan birining nomidir. U Kaliforniya shtatiga qarashli Los-Anjeles okrugi g‘arbida joylashgan Malibu shahri sharafiga nomlangan. Qayd etish kerakki, birinchi marta “Malibu” nomi 1962-yilda paydo bo‘lgan.

Abbreviatsiya – pereyonimlar yasalishining keng tarqalgan usuli sifatida namoyon bo‘ladi.

Ba’zi pereyonimlar metaforik ko‘chma nomlar bilan parallel ishlatiladi. Masalan, “Chevrolet Captiva”ga nisbatan “Tartan oti” nomi qo‘llanadi.

Transportlar har xil sohalarda va turfa maqsadlarda qo‘llanishiga qarab ham turlanadi.

Jumladan, ular madaniy turmushda shaxsiy avtoulav, jamoa transporti, qishloq xo‘jaligi va qurilishda, harbiy soha, tibbiyot texnikasi sifatida qo‘llanib keladi.

Xulosa shuki, dunyo tilshunosligida turli tizimdagi tillarning leksikoni, onomastikasini qiyosiy aspektda o'rganishga bag'ishlanayotgan tadqiqotlar salmog'i kundan kunga ortib bormoqda. Turli onomastik birliklar qatorida pereyonimlarning tilda leksik-semantik, milliy-madaniy, badiiy matnda esa lingvostilistik, poetonimlik xususiyatlarini, bir tildan boshqa bir tizimdagi tilga o'zlashish omillarini, tarjimada o'z asliyatini saqlab qolish sabablarini aniqlash hozirgi tilshunoslik ilmi oldida turgan dolzarb vazifalardan biridir.

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